

List of Cimicomorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) Described by Foreign Scientists in Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum from Turkey. Part II

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ABSTRACT: This study was conducted based on material collected and identified by foreign scientists between 1932 and 1972 and housed in the Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum (NTM) at the Directorate of Plant Protection Central Research Institute in the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry.

The first part of the contribution to the knowledge of Heteroptera fauna of Turkey covered the infraorder Pentatomomorpha. The second part includes the infraorders Cimicomorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha. For this purpose, 77 species and subspecies belonging to 53 genera belonging to 8 families were discussed in this study.

Current names for many species are provided and corrected.

KEYWORDS: Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Cimicomorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, Turkey.

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INTRODUCTION

Directorate of Plant Protection Central Research Institute was founded in Ankara in 1934.

It was established as a Phytopathology department under the name of Central Struggle Institute under the direction of Prof. Dr. G. GASSNER. In 1938, The

Department of Entomology was opened with Prof. Dr. F.S.BODENHEIMER and studies on pests have gained even more speed. Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum (NTM) which was established within the scope of the Central Research Institute of Agricultural Protection in 1961 is one of the oldest and most well-established Entomology museums in Turkey.

More than 35.000 specimens belonging to 3.000 species, whose collection dates back to the 1930s, are preserved in the museum, which is increasing the number of examples with projects.

In the museum collection, there are still quite old samples based on the establishment of the museum, new samples added to the inventory by the existing projects and samples based on newly defined species, called type samples.

Among these specimens are species collected and identified by foreign scientists.

Data from the museum collection were cataloged and published two times, in the years 1966 and 1971.

Moreover, between 2002 and 2007, some part of non-defined samples identification was provided and information about 1874 species in the museum collection was recorded to the database program with the project "The Enrichment of Insect Collection of Turkey Plant Protection Museum and Development of a Database".

In the last period, both new sample entrance and donations especially from Bornova Plant Protection Research and Adana Biological Control Research Direction occurred. That increases the samples at the museum. This situation caused an increase in the number of samples of Heteroptera Latreille, 1810 (Hemiptera) in the museum.

There are 3417 examples of diagnosis belonging to 22 families and 447 species of Heteroptera in the museum.

Turkey, is a mountainous mass averaging about 1000 meters in height. It has several

climatically distinct regions. The topographic and climatic structure give to the country the opportunity of hosts a rich and diverse fauna and flora. It has been known to possess a rich fauna of Heteroptera. Thus, faunistic and systematic studies about the Heteroptera have been conducted by both foreign and native researchers in Turkey (Hoberlandt, 1955; Önder, 1976, Önder et al., 2006; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998, 1999, 2003; Péricart, 1983; Yardım, 1990; Kıyak et al., 2004, Kıyak & Akar, 2010, Kıyak & Baş 2021; Bolu et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009, 2011a, 2011b; Fent & Aktaç, 2009, Fent, 2011, Fent & Dursun, 2019; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013 a, b., 2014; Maral et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı, 2014, Küçükbasmacı et al., 2016; Yazıcı et al., 2015a,b, 2016, 2017a,b, 2019; Çerçi et al., 2018, Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019, Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Pehlivan & Atakan, 2020).

In this study, 77 species and subspecies belonging to 53 genera belonging to 8 families were discussed. In this study, the current names for many species provided and corrected taxa were revised and locality information updated.

MATERIAL and METHODS

Here is present a list of all the genus- and species-group taxa housed in the Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum (NTM) and described by E. Wagner, G. Karel, L. Hoberlandt, F.S. Bodenheimer, M. S. K. Ghauri, N. C. E. Miller, C. I. E. Coll ve B. Ubarov.

The list is divided systematically according to infraorders and families, with families listed alphabetically within each infraorder. Names of genus and species-group taxa are listed alphabetically within each family in their original combination and original spelling. For this purpose, 77 species and subspecies belonging to 53 genera belonging to 8 families were discussed in the study.

LIST of TAXA**Infraorder Cimicomorpha****Anthocoridae Fieber, 1836*****Anthocoris butleri* Le Quesne, 1954**

Materials examined: Kastamonu, 29.06.1972, ♀, Leg. M. Ergüden (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri at 1974); Mersin, 15.09.1974, ♀ (on *Pitus malus*), Leg. C.I.E. COLL (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

Notes: *Anthocoris nemoralis butleri* Le Quesne, 1954 upgraded as *Anthocoris butleri* Le Quesne, 1954 by Wagner, 1957b:103 (Aukema & Rieger, 1996).

***Anthocoris gallarumulmi* (De Geer, 1773)**

Materials examined: İzmir, Bornova, 29.09.1934, 4 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂ (on *Prunus dulcis*), Leg. B. Uvarov (Det. B.Uvarov, 1934).

***Anthocoris nemoralis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Keçiören, 24.05.1961, ♀, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Gaziantep, 10.06.1969, ♂, Leg. M. Y. Çelik (M. S. K. Ghauri at 1969); Mersin, 15.10.1974, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

Notes: This species is designated as *Anthocoris* sp. by M. S. K. Ghauri at 1969. It was found in the study that *Anthocoris nemoralis* (Fabricius, 1794).

***Anthocoris sibiricus* Reuter, 1875**

Materials examined: Ankara, Çamlıdere, Çamkoru, 6.09.1975, ♀, Leg. N.Aysev, (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri 1976).

***Cardiastethus nazarenus* Reuter, 1884**

Materials examined: Mersin, Erdemli, 6.09.1969, ♀, 3 ♂♂ (on *Pseudococcus citri*), Leg. C. Sokman (Det. J. Carayon, 1970).

***Orius (Heterorius) minutus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Materials examined: İzmir, 29.08.1936, ♀, ♂, Leg. unknown (Det. B. Uvarov, 1936), Bornova, 24.08.1932, 2 ♂♂, Leg. Müze, (Det. B. Uvarov, 1934); Mersin, 15.10.1974, 2 ♀♀, ♂ (on *Pyrus malus*), Leg. unknown (Det. M.S.K.Ghauri, 1975); Samsun, 17.04.1972, 2 ♀♀, Leg. R. Çamlıdere, (Det. M.S.K. Ghauri, 1975).

Notes: This species was diagnosed as *Orius* sp. by M. S. K. Ghauri at 1975. However, it was determined as *Orius (Heterorius) minutus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the study. Also, it was identified as *Triphleps minutus* by B. Uvarov (İzmir, 29.08.1936) in 1936. But, *Triphleps minutus* is a synonym for *Orius (Heterorius) minutus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

***Orius horvathi* (Reuter, 1884)**

Materials examined: Mersin, 15.10.1974, ♂, Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

Notes: This species was registered as *Orius* sp. in the Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum. However, it was determined as *Orius horvathi* (Reuter, 1884) in the study.

***Orius (Orius) niger niger* (Wolff, 1811)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Çubuk, 15.05.1961, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).İzmir, Menemen, 6.09.1977, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. Müze, (Det. J. Carayon 1977).

Temnostethus (Montandoniella) dacicus (Puton, 1888)

Materials examined: Amasya, 11.04.1972, ♀, ♂, Leg. H. Kiroğlu, (Det. M.S.K. Ghauri, 1975)

Notes: It was identified as *Montandoniella dacica* Puton, 1888 by M.S.K. Ghauri (Amasya, 11.04.1972) in 1975. However, *Montandoniella dacica* Puton, 1888b: 256. Lithuania (Pericárt, 1972: 81, as "type"): macr. ♂, Romania, Bucarest (Aukema & Rieger, 1996). This species was diagnosed as *Montandoniella dacica* Puton by Ghauri in 1975. *Montandoniella dacica* Puton is a synonym for *Temnostethus (Montandoniella) dacicus* (Puton, 1888).

Miridae Hahn, 1831***Adelphocoris lineolatus (Goeze, 1778)***

Materials examined: Elazığ, Sivrice, 23.07.1961, 6 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961), Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, ♀, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Niğde, 14.06.1965, ♂, Leg. Ş. Velibeyoğlu (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1969).

Adelphocoris vandalicus (Rossi, 1790)

Materials examined: Elazığ, Sivrice, 23.07.1961, ♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); İstanbul, 04.08.1961, 3 ♀♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Agnocoris rubicundus (Fallen, 1807)

Materials examined: Kastamonu, 29.06.1972, ♀, Leg. M. Ergüden (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

Alloeonotus fulvipes (Scopoli, 1763)

Materials examined: Ankara. Bağlum, 08.06.1961, 4 ♀♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1962).

Notes: *Alloeonotus fulvipes* var. *seperandus* Horvath, 1888: 179 upgraded to species by Josifov, 1959b: 359; syn. Sienkiewicz, 1963: 463 (Aukema & Rieger, 1999).

Aphanosoma italicum A. Costa, 1842

Materials examined: Ankara, Bağlum, 08.06.1961, 5 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Atractotomus magnicornis (Fallén, 1807)

Materials examined: Mersin, 15.10.1974, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. unknown, (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

Notes: This species was defined genus level as *Atractotomus* sp. by Ghauri in 1975. In this study, it was updated as *Atractotomus magnicornis* (Fallén, 1807).

Brachycoleus decolor Reuter, 1887

Materials examined: Isparta, Şakikaraağaç, 27.06.1972, ♀ (on *Triticum* sp.) Leg. G. Altınayar (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974); Kayseri, Develi, 14.05.1961, ♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1962).

Calocoris roseomaculatus saucius Linnavuori, 1951

Materials examined: Ankara, Bağlum, 08.06.1961, 2 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961), Çubuk, Baraj, 16.05.1961, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, ♂, Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel

(Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Notes: *Calocoris saucius* Linnavuori, 1951b:104 (downgraded by Linnavuori, 1960:63) (Aukema & Rieger, 1999).

***Camponotidea saundersi* (Puton, 1874)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Çubuk, Baraj, 15.05.1961, ♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Campylomma diversicorne* Reuter, 1878**

Materials examined: Diyarbakır, 2.07.1975, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂ (on *Gossypium*) Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1976).

***Campylomma lindbergi* Hoberlandt, 1953**

Materials examined: Gaziantep, 18.03.1969, 9 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂, Leg. M. Y. Çelik (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1969).

***Closterotomus annulus* (Brullé, 1832)**

Materials examined: Adana, 1971, ♂, Leg. Z. Soylu (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1971); Ankara, Bağlum, 08.06.1961, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1962).

Notes: Wagner (1959i: 344) subdivided this species in *Calocoris annulus* (= *fuscescens*, *fuliginosus*) and *C. nebulosus*, with unclear synonymy of *C. collaris*. This subdivision, though accepted by some authors (e. g. Tamanini, 1981), is not substantiated and not followed here (Aukema & Rieger, 1999).

***Closterotomus fulvomaculatus* (De Geer, 1773)**

Materials examined: Ankara, 08.06.1961, ♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1962).

***Closterotomus norwegicus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Materials examined: Amasya, 29.05.1974, ♀, Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975); Ankara, Bağlum, 08.06.1961, ♀, ♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1962), Çubuk, 09.06.1966, ♀, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967); Sinop, Gerze, 17.06.1975, ♀, Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1976).

***Compsidolon salicellum* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1841)**

Materials examined: Giresun, 16.06.1964, ♀, 5 ♂♂, 28.08.1964, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, 23.08.1965, ♂, Leg. M. Işık (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1965).

Notes: This species is diagnosed as *Psallus salicellus* by Ghauri in 1965. However, the species name is updated as *Compsidolon salicellum* (Herrich-Schäffer).

***Creontiades pallidus* (Rambur, 1839)**

Materials examined: İzmir, Kemalpaşa, 03.11.1966, ♂, Leg. F. Önder (Det. E. Wagner, 1967).

***Deraeocoris* (*Camptobrochis*) *serenus* (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**

Materials examined: İzmir, Torbalı, 04.11.1966, ♀, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967); Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, 2 ♀♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Deraeocoris* (*Deraeocoris*) *rutilus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838)**

Materials examined: Kayseri, Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Deraeocoris* (*Deraeocoris*) *trifasciatus* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Bağlum, 08.06.1961, 3 ♀♀, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961), Keçiören, 24.05.1961, 2 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Deraeocoris (Knightocapsus) lutescens (Schilling, 1837)

Materials examined: Adana, 6.07.1971, 4 ♂♂, Leg. T. Süzer, (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1972); Samsun, Bafra, 02.10.1972, 2 ♀♀, ♂, Leg. R. Çamlidere (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

Dryophilocoris flavoquadrimaculatus (De Geer, 1773)

Materials examined: Ankara, Keçiören, 02.06.1961, ♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Glaphyrocoris lunigerus (Horváth, 1913)

Materials examined: Gaziantep, 06.07.1971, ♀, Leg. M. Y. Çelik (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1972).

Heterocordylus (Bothrocranum) erythrophthalmus (Hahn, 1833)

Materials examined: Ankara, Keçiören, 24.05.1961, 3 ♀♀, ♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Horistus (Horistus) bimaculatus (Jakovlev, 1884)

Materials examined: Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, ♀, ♂, Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, ♀, ♂, Leg. G. Karel. (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Notes: *Horistus* Fieber, 1861b: 66, 1861: 268 (syn. Reuter, 1875b: 79, with *Lopus*: as subgenus of *Capsodes* by Wagner, 1951k: 132, 1952h: 71; as genus by Chérot, 1997a: 126 (Aukema & Rieger, 1999). This species was described as *Capsodes bimaculatus* (Jakovlev) by Wagner in 1961.

Horistus infuscatus (Brullé, 1832)

Materials examined: İzmir, Tire, 16.12.1966, ♂, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967).

Notes: The records from Cyprus, Iran, Israel and Syria probably refer to *Horistus bimaculatus* and *H. turcomanus*. Old records from Egypt are referred here to *H. turcomanus*. The record by Chérot (1997a) from "Hongri", Tranczén" (=Slovakia, Trencin) is based on mislabelling (see Horvath, 1898d: 35). Also, the record from Italy (Genoa) by Chérot (1997a) needs confirmation (Aukema & Rieger, 1999).

Horistus (Primihoristus) orientalis (Gmelin, 1790)

Materials examined: Ankara, Bağlum, 08.06.1961, 5 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1962); Kayseri, Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, 2 ♀♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1962).

Notes: *Cimex cingulatus* Fabricius, 1787: 307 (junior primary homonym of *Cimex cingulatus* Fabricius, 1775). Chérot, 1997a; Wagner, 1951k (*cingulatus*, *lineatus*), 1959d (*cingulatus*, *lineatus*) (Aukema & Rieger, 1999). This species was described as *Capsodes cingulatus* Fabricius by Wagner in 1961.

Isometopus intrusus (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)

Materials examined: Gaziantep, 6.07.1971, ♀, ♂, Leg. M. Y. Çelik, (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1972).

Liocoris tripustulatus (Fabricius, 1781)

Materials examined: İstanbul, 04.08.1961, 2 ♂♂; Malatya, Yeşilyurt, 22.07.1961, ♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Lygus gemellatus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)**

Materials examined: Elazığ, Sivrice, 23.07.1961, 7 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Malatya, Yeşilyurt, 22.07.1961, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Nevşehir, Avanos, 1.06.1966, 4 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂, Leg. Ş. Velibeyoğlu (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1967).

Notes: *Exolygus* Wagner, 1949a: 37 (as subgenus of *Lygus*). Type species by original designation: *Cimex pratensis* Linnaeus, 1758. Placed on the Official Index of Rejected and Invalid Generic Names (Opinion 667/1963) (Aukema & Rieger, 1999). This species was described as *Exolygus gemellatus* (Herrich-Schäffer) by Wagner in 1961.

***Lygus pratensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Materials examined: Elazığ, Sivrice, 23.07.1961, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); İstanbul, 04.08.1961, 2 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); İzmir, 06.06.1966, ♂, Leg. F. Önder (Det. E. Wagner, 1967), Gümüşsuyu, 11.04.1967, ♀, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967); Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, ♀, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Notes: *Exolygus* Wagner, 1949a: 37 (as subgenus of *Lygus*). Type species by original designation: *Cimex pratensis* Linnaeus, 1758. Placed on the Official Index of Rejected and Invalid Generic Names (Opinion 667/1963) (Aukema & Rieger, 1999). This species was described as *Exolygus pratensis* (Linnaeus) by Wagner in 1961 and 1967.

***Lygus rugulipennis* Poppius, 1911**

Materials examined: Elazığ, Sivrice, 23.07.1961, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, 7 ♀♀, 9 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961), Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Malatya, Yeşilyurt, 22.07.1961, ♀, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Notes: *Exolygus* Wagner, 1949a: 37 (as subgenus of *Lygus*). Type species by original designation: *Cimex pratensis* Linnaeus, 1758. Placed on the Official Index of Rejected and Invalid Generic Names (Opinion 667/1963) (Aukema & Rieger, 1999). This species was described as *Exolygus rugulipennis* Poppius by Wagner in 1961.

***Macrolophus melanotoma* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Materials examined: Antalya, 15.10.1974, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. unknown, (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975); İzmir, 05.11.1966, ♂, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967).

Notes: *Macrolophus caliginosus* (Wagner, 1951a: 29) synonymed by Carapezza in 1995a: 297 (Aukema & Rieger, 1999). This species was described as *Macrolophus caliginosus* by E. Wagner in 1967 and by Ghauri in 1975.

***Malacocoris chlorizans* (Panzer, 1794)**

Materials examined: Kastamonu, 29.06.1972, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. R. Çamlıdere (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

***Megacoelum infusum* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1837)**

Materials examined: Gaziantep, Nizip, 14.06.1971, ♂, Leg. M. Y. Çelik (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1972).

***Oncotylus pyrethri* (Becker, 1864)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Çubuk, Baraj, 23.05.1961, 2 ♀♀, ♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Orthocephalus parvulus* Reuter, 1891**

Materials examined: Ankara, Çubuk, Baraj, 15.05.1961, ♀, 22.05.1961, ♂, Gölbaşı, 27.05.1961, ♀, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Orthops campestris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Materials examined: Samsun, Bafra, 02.10.1972, ♀, ♂, Leg. R. Çamlıdere (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

***Orthops (Orthops) kalmii* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Materials examined: Malatya, Yeşilyurt, 22.07.1961, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Pachytomella passerinii* (A. Costa, 1842)**

Materials examined: İzmir, Selçuk, 05.11.1966, ♂, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1977).

Notes: Acting as first reviser, A. Costa (1853: 55) selected *minor* as the valid name giving it precedence over *passerinii*. The reverse act by Reuter (1890a: 254) was generally accepted but required a ruling from the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature.

***Phytocoris reuteri* Saunders, 1876**

Materials examined: Artvin, Hopa, 15.07.1972, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. İ. Bozan (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

***Phytocoris tiliae* (Fabricius, 1777)**

Materials examined: Kastamonu, 30.06.1972, 3 ♂♂, Leg. R. Çamlıdere (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

***Platyporus dorsalis* Reuter 1890**

Materials examined: Ankara, Çubuk, Baraj, 15.05.1961, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Psallus kolenatii* (Flor, 1860)**

Materials examined: Çankırı, Merkez, Çiviköy, 9.07.1974, 2 ♀♀, (*Triticum* sp.) Eldivan, Çiftlik, 10.07.1974, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, (*Triticum* sp.) Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1976).

***Taylorilygus apicalis* (Fieber, 1861)**

Materials examined: İzmir, Torbalı, 04.11.1966, ♂, Leg. F. Önder (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Thermocoris rivalis rivalis* (Horváth, 1894)**

Materials examined: Kayseri, Develi, 14.06.1961, 2 ♀♀, ♂, Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Trigonotylus pulchellus* (Hahn, 1834)**

Materials examined: İzmir, Torbalı, 04.11.1966, ♂, Leg. F. Önder (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Trigonotylus ruficornis* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Materials examined: Kırşehir, Malya, 03.05.1961, ♀, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Utopnia torquata* (Puton, 1881)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Gölbaşı, 27.05.1961, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Nabidae A. Costa, 1853

***Himacerus (Aptus) mirmicoides* (O. Costa, 1834)**

Materials examined: Artvin, Hopa, 15.07.1972, 4 ♀♀, Leg. İ. Bozan (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

***Nabis (Nabis) ferus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Materials examined: Kırklareli, Pınarhisar, 10.07.1974, 2 ♀♀, ♂ (on Rice), Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

***Nabis (Nabis) punctatus punctatus* A. Costa, 1847**

Materials examined: Diyarbakır, Ergani, 21.07.1969, 2 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂, Leg. S. Ergül (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1972); Malatya, 5.08.1969, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Leg. S. Ergül (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1972).

***Nabis (Nabis) palifer* Seidenstucker, 1954**

Materials examined: Nevşehir, Ürgüp, 23.06.1966, ♀, ♂, Leg. Ş. Velibeyoğlu (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1967).

***Prostemma (Prostemma) guttula guttula* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Çubuk, Baraj, 16.05.1961, ♀, 22.05.1961, ♀, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Notes: This species was diagnosed as *Prostemma guttula* (Fabricius) by Wagner in 1961.

Reduviidae Latreille, 1807

***Oncocephalus plumicornis* (Germar, 1822)**

Materials examined: Nevşehir, Avanos, 03.06.1966, ♀, ♂, Leg. Ş. Velibeyoğlu (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1969).

***Oncocephalus squalidus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Materials examined: Şanlıurfa, Ceylanpınar, 18.05.1961, ♀, Leg. G. Karel. (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

***Phymata crassipes* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Materials examined: Ankara, Keçiören, 24.05.1961, ♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Notes: Wagner dealt with in the Phymatidae family of *Phymata crassipes* (Fabricius) in 1961. However, Aukema & Rieger (1996) discussed this species in the Phymatinae subfamily from the Reduviidae family.

***Reduvius pallipes* Klug, 1830**

Materials examined: Aydın, 10.05.1963, ♀, Leg. A. Çekli (Det. E. Wagner, 1967).

***Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) iracundus* (Poda, 1761)**

Materials examined: İzmir, 06.05.1966, ♀, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967).

Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) punctiventris (Herrich-Schäffer, 1846)

Materials examined: Kayseri, Hisarcık, 15.06.1961, ♂, Leg. G. Karel (Det. E. Wagner, 1961).

Vachiria spinosa (Jakovlev, 1874)

Materials examined: Denizli, Buldan, 18.04.1967, ♀, ♂, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967).

Tingidae Laporte, 1832

Dictyla echii (Schrank, 1782)

Materials examined: Ankara, Bağlum, 01.06.1961, ♀, ♂, Çubuk, Baraj, 15.05.1961, 2 ♀♀, Elmadag, 01.06.1961, ♀, ♂, Leg. E. Wagner (Det. E. Wagner, 1961); Tokat, 24.04.1974, ♀, Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

Kalama aethiops (Horváth, 1905)

Materials examined: İzmir, Kemalpaşa, 03.11.1967, ♂, Leg. N. Çağatay (Det. E. Wagner, 1967).

Notes: *Dictyonota aethiops* Horváth, 1905a: 563 was synonymized *Kalama aethiops* (Horváth, 1905) (Aukema & Rieger, 1996). This species was diagnosed as *Dictyonota aethiops* Horváth, 1905 by Wagner in 1967.

Physatocheila confinis Horváth, 1905

Materials examined: Çorum, 21.04.1972, ♀, ♂, Leg. H. Kiroğlu (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1974).

Notes: According to Péricart (1982, 1983) this species seems well separated morphologically from *P. dumetorum* in the eastern part of its area, but it is difficult or even impossible to separate them in the western part. From the very short redescription of *Monanthia quadrimaculata* by A. Costa (1843) it is not clear whether he was dealing with *Physatocheila confinis* or *Ph. dumetorum* (Aukema & Rieger, 1996).

Tingis (Tropidocheila) hellenica (Puton, 1877)

Materials examined: Mersin, Mut, 04.07.1969, 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Leg. M. A. Ambaroğlu (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1969).

Tingis (Tingis) cardui (Linnaeus, 1758)

Materials examined: Tokat, 24.04.1974, ♂ (on *Triticum* sp.), Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

Infraorder Nepomorpha

Belostomatidae Leach, 1815

L. patruelis (Stal, 1854)

Materials examined: Edirne, 6.06.1972, ♀, Leg. İ. Yurtsever (Det. M.S.K.Ghauri, 1974).

Notonectidae Latreille, 1802

Notonecta maculata Fabricius, 1798

Materials examined: Edirne, İpsala, 11.07.1974, ♀, ♂ (on Rice) Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

Infraorder Gerromorpha

Gerridae Leach, 1815

Gerris (Gerris) thoracicus Schummel, 1832

Materials examined: Tekirdağ, Çorlu, 10.07.1974, 2 ♀♀, ♂, Leg. unknown (Det. M. S. K. Ghauri, 1975).

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